

Synthesis of some New Heterocyclic Systems bearing 2-Phenyl-6-iodo-4(3H)-quinazolinon-3-yl Moiety as Antibacterial Agents

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Manuscript received 6 March 1995, revised 18 March 1996, accepted 24 July 1996

A number of heterobicyclic systems bearing 2-phenyl-6-iodo-4(3H)-quinazolinon-3-yl moiety have been synthesised by interaction of 3-amino-2-phenyl-6-iodo-4(3H)-quinazolinone with bifunctional compounds followed by cyclisation in different media. Some of the compounds possess high activity against bacteria.

The heterocyclic nitrogen compounds especially quinazolinone derivatives play a vital role in many biological processes and as synthetic drugs¹⁻⁴. It was thought worthwhile to incorporate some additional heterocyclic moieties in the quinazolinone nucleus to study their effect on biological activities of the quinazolinones.

Results and Discussion

Iodinated 3-amino-2-phenyl-4(3H)-quinazolinone (**1**) was synthesised according to the following Scheme⁵⁻⁷:

Acylation and/or alkylation of compound **1** using ethyl chloroformate, ethyl acetoacetate, chloroacetyl chloride and ethyl chloroacetate in different solvents afforded monoaryl/alkyl derivatives (**2c-d**). Compound **2c** was reacted with potassium thiocyanate and diethyl malonate to give **2e**, and **2f** respectively, while compound **2d** upon hydrazinolysis afforded **2g** (Scheme 1).

The interaction between compound **1** and chloroacetamide in DMF⁸ led to direct formation of 4-oxo-1,2,4-triazino[2,3-c]quinazoline derivative (**3**). Compound **2a** and/or **2b** on reaction with hydrazine hydrate in ethanol gave the starting compound **1** instead of the acid hydrazide. In addition, acidic cyclisation of **2f** using acetic anhydride gave 6-iodo-2-phenyl-3,1,4-benzoxazinone. On the other hand, cyclocondensation of **2b** with substituted phenylhydrazine and/or cyanoguanidine in glacial acetic acid gave 2-benzoylamino-5-iodoanthranilic acid⁴. The probable mechanism of these reactions are shown in Scheme 2. Only one acetic acid hydrazide (**2g**) was obtained from the treatment of **2d** with hydrazine hydrate in ethanol. The original plan of the present work was to synthesise the heterobicyclic systems. Thus, 5-dihydro-3-methyl-4-(6'-iodo-2'-phenyl-4'(3H)-quinazolinon-3'-yl)-1,2,4-triazin-6(1H)-one (**5**) and 5-dihydro-3-phenyl-4-(6'-iodo-2'-phenyl-4'(3H)-quinazolinon-3'-yl)triazin-6(1H)-one (**6**) were alternatively

synthesised in good yields via the reaction of **2g** with acetic anhydride and/or benzoyl chloride in pyridine (Scheme 1). The structures of **5** and **6** were supported by their mass spectral fragmentation (Scheme 4).

TABLE I—ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY DATA (INHIBITION ZONE, mm) OF HETEROCYCLIC SYSTEMS 3-15

Compd no	Sa	Sm	Bs	Ca	Ec
3	—	12	22	—	18
5	22	15	28	14	24
6	23	14	20	10	19
7	18	15	12	—	15
8	15	16	14	20	13
9	20	21	18	21	20
10	14	17	—	12	13
11	20	17	14	—	12
12	15	—	17	16	13
13	—	20	18	—	16
15a	17	18	21	24	12
15b	19	15	14	11	24
15c	20	16	13	12	23
Gentamycin	29	28	25	21	31

Sa = *S. aureus*, Sm = *S. marcescens*, Bs = *B. subtilis*, Ca = *C. albicans*, Ec = *E. coli*

In a similar manner, work was extended to synthesise 5-dihydro-6-oxo-1,2,4-triazino[2,3-c]quinazoline (**7**), 1H-2,6-tetrahydro-4-(6'-iodo-2'-phenyl-4'(3H)-quinazolinon-3'-yl)-1,4-diazin-3,5-dione (**8**) and 2,6-tetrahydro-4-(6'-iodo-2'-phenyl-4'(3H)-quinazolinon-3'-yl)-1,4-thiazin-3,5-dione (**9**) by treatment of **2c** with ammonium acetate in glacial acetic acid¹¹, ethyl glycinate hydrochloride in pyridine and/or thioglycolic acid in pyridine (Scheme 1). The structure of these compounds was further confirmed by mass spectrometry. Thus, the mass spectrum of **9** exhibited a molecular peak 477 (0.25%) and the base peak 348 (100%) corresponding to 2-phenyl-6-iodo-4(3H)-quinazolinone radical (Scheme 4). Also, compound **2c** was cyclised using ethanol-pyridine (by equal volume mixture) to give 2-dihydro-4-(6'-iodo-2'-phenyl-4'(3H)-quinazolinon-3'-yl)-

Scheme 1

1,4-thiazin-3,5-dione (10) (Scheme 3).

As a point of interest, it was found that cyano compounds such as ethyl cyanoacetate (in piperidine), malononitrile (in piperidine) and potassium cyanate (in ethanol) had reacted with compound 2c to yield the normal addition products^{12,13} 2-imino-5-dihydro-1-(6'-iodo-2'-phenyl-4'(3H)-quinazolinon-3'-yl)-3-ethylcarboxypyrol-5-one (11), 2-imino-4-dihydro-1-(6'-iodo-2'-phenyl-4'(3H)-quinazolinon-3'-yl)-3-cyanopyrol-5-one (12) and 2-dihydro-3-(6'-iodo-2'-phenyl-4'(3H)-quinazolinon-3'-yl)-1,4-oxazol-3,5-dione (13) (Scheme 3). The mass spectral

fragments of 12 are shown in Scheme 4.

Finally, the heterobicyclic systems of the type 15a-e were obtained by condensation of 3-amino-6-iodo-2-phenyl-4(3H)-quinazolinone (1) with 2-substituted-3,1-benzoxazin-4-one (14a-e)¹⁴ (Scheme 3). The compounds were supported by their mass spectra, thus the spectrum of 15b showed a molecular ion peak at m/z 632 and the base peak at 77 (100%) (Scheme 4).

Antibacterial activity: All the compounds were tested *in vivo* for their antibacterial activity against a variety of bacteria, such as *S. aureus*, *S. marcescens*, *B. subtilis*, *C.*

albicans and *E. coli* in DMF at a concentration of 3 mg ml⁻¹ following the method of cup-diffusion techniques¹⁵ and using gentamycin as standard compound at concentration of 0.03 mg ml⁻¹ (distilled water). The results (Table 1) showed that compound 5 containing 6-hydroxy-3-methyl-1,2,4-triazine moiety at N-3 quinazolinone possesses a significant antibacterial activity as compared to gentamycin, against *B. subtilis* and *E. coli*, while compound 6 containing 6-hydroxy-3-phenyl-1,2,4-triazine moiety at the same position did not show significant antibacterial activity. On the other hand, compound 13 showed a higher effect compared to other compounds towards *S. marcescens*. Addition of second quinazolinone moiety towards the parent substance resulted a promising activity of all tested compounds and/or larger than the gentamycin towards *C. albicans*.

Experimental

M.ps. are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 293 spectrophotometer, ¹H nmr spectra (DMSO-d₆) on a Varian EM-390 (90 MHz) instrument using TMS as internal standard and mass spectra on a GCMSqp 1000 ex Shimadzu instrument at 70 eV. All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses. Purity of the compounds was detected by tlc using CCl₄-ethyl acetate (9 : 1) as a solvent. Compounds 1 and 14a-c were pre-

pared by the reported method¹⁴.

Compounds 2a-g. General procedure :

Preparation of 2a and/or 2d : A solution of 1 (0.01 mol) in dioxane (30 ml) was treated with ethyl chloroformate and/or ethyl chloroacetate (0.015 mol). The reaction mixture was then cooled, triethylamine (0.015 mol) added dropwise, refluxed for 6 h, filtered while hot, concentrated, and cooled. The solid obtained was dried and crystallised from ethanol : 2a (75%), m.p. 223° (EtOH); 2d (72%), 152° (EtOH), ν_{\max} 3 300–3 200 (NH), 3 040 (aromatic CH), 2 950 (aliphatic CH), 1 760, 1 680 (2C=O), 1 630–1 600 (C=N), 1 480–1 460, 1 430 (def. CH₂, CH₃), 1 210 (CN), 920, 870 and 820 cm⁻¹ (phenyl and aryl groups).

Preparation 2b : A suspension of 1 (0.01 mol) in ethyl acetoacetate (20 ml) was refluxed for 2 h, and the solvent was then removed by evaporation. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol, (79%), m.p. 140° (EtOH), ν_{\max} 3 500–3 300 (OH, NH), 3 070 (aromatic CH), 2 920 (aliphatic CH), 1 800, 1 780 and 1 700 (C=O), 1 620–1 570 (C=N), 1 480, 1 450 (def. CH₂, (CH₃)₂), 1 210 (CN), 920, 870 and 820 cm⁻¹ (aryl and phenyl groups).

Preparation of 2c : To a solution of 1 (0.01 mol) in DMF (15 ml), chloroacetyl chloride (0.015 mol) was added dropwise, then stirred for 1 h at room temperature and poured onto ice. The solid obtained was crystallised from glacial acetic acid, (83%), m.p. 209° (AcOH), ν_{\max} 3 150 (NH), 3 070 (aromatic CH), 2 950 (aliphatic CH), 1 720, 1 680–1 650 (C=O), 1 610–1 580 (C=N), 1 510–1 480, 1 450–1 440 (def. CH₂), 1 210 (CN), 920, 840 (phenyl and aryl groups) and 710 cm⁻¹ (C–Cl).

Preparation of 2e : A mixture of 2c (0.01 mol) and potassium thiocyanate (0.02 mol) in DMF (20 ml) was refluxed for 4 h, then cooled and poured on ice. The solid obtained was crystallised from DMF, (80%), m.p. 127° (DMF).

Preparation of 2f : A mixture of 2c (0.005 mol) and diethyl malonate (1 ml) in piperidine (15 ml) was refluxed for 2 h, then cooled and poured on crushed ice containing a few drops of HCl. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol, (60%), m.p. 235° (EtOH), ν_{\max} 3 550 (OH), 3 120 (NH), 3 020 (aromatic CH), 2 950, 2 870 (aliphatic CH), 1 820, 1 800–1 770, 1 750 and 1 690 (C=O), 1 620, 1 590 (C=N), 1 480, 1 450 (def. CH₂, CH₃), 1 210 (CN), 940, 840 cm⁻¹ (aryl and phenyl groups), δ 1.7 (3H, s, CH₃), 1.8, 4.11, 3.46 (2H, s, each of 2 × CH₂), 7.54–7.93 (5H, m, ArH), 7.93–8.4 (3H, m, ArH), 10.2 (1H, s, HO-CO) and 11.1 (1H, s, NH).

4-Oxo-1,2,4-triazino[2,3-c]quinazoline derivative (3) : An equimolar mixture of 1 and chloroacetamide in DMF (25 ml) was refluxed overnight, then cooled, diluted with cold water and the solid obtained was crystallised from ethanol, (60%), m.p. 145° (EtOH), ν_{\max} 3 320 (NH), 3 060

Scheme 3

(aromatic CH), 2 940 (aliphatic CH), 1 680–1 670 (C=O), 1 610–1 550 (C=N), 1 490, 1 470 (def. CH₂), 1 250 (CN), 900, 850–830 cm⁻¹ (aryl and phenyl groups).

Cyclocondensation of 2b with phenylhydrazine and/or cyanoguanidine :

2-Benzoylamino-5-iodobenzoic acid (4) : A mixture of **2b** (0.005 mol) and phenyl hydrazine or cyanoguanidine (0.0075 mol) in glacial acetic acid (30 ml) containing anhydrous sodium acetate (0.5 g) was refluxed overnight, then concentrated to one-third of its volume and cooled. The solid obtained was crystallised from glacial acetic acid, (50%), m.p. 265° (AcOH), ν_{\max} 3 500–3 040 (OH, NH), 1 710, 1 680–1 650 (C=O), 1 620–1 590 (C=C), 900, 850–830, 790 (aryl and phenyl groups) and 700–680 cm⁻¹ (C–I), δ 7.55–7.96 (5H, m, ArH), 7.99–8.50 (3H, m,

benzoprotons), 8.55 (1H, s, carboxylic), and 12.10 (1H, s, NH).

Acetic acid hydrazide 2g : A mixture of **2d** (0.01 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.02 mol) in ethanol (50 ml) was refluxed for 6 h and then concentrated. The solid obtained was crystallised from benzene-ethanol, (65%), m.p. 207° (EtOH), ν_{\max} 3 420–3 300 (NH₂), 3 150–3 090 (NH), 3 010 (aromatic CH), 2 980, 2800 (aliphatic CH), 1 720, 1 680–1 660 (C=O), 1 620, 1 600 (C=C, C=N), 1 470, 1 440 (def. CH₂), 1 200 (CN), 850 and 800 cm⁻¹ (aryl and phenyl groups).

3,4-Disubstituted-5-dihydro-1,2,4-triazin-6-one (5) : A mixture of **2g** (0.005 mol) and acetic anhydride (20 ml) was refluxed for 2 h, then concentrated down to 4 ml and cooled. The solid obtained was crystallised from ethanol, (30%),

α m/e 348 (100%)
 β m/e 305(4.45%)
 γ m/e 245(34.20%)
 m/e 128(0.89%)
 m/e 77(0.65%)

α m/e 349 (0.50%)
 β m/e 245(1.64%)
 γ m/e 228(0.23%)
 m/e 105(77.67%)
 m/e 77(100%)

α m/e 122 (2.35%)
 β m/e 164(12.80%)
 γ m/e 165(17.63%)
 m/e 228(0.82%)
 m/e 77(100%)

α m/e 348 (100%)
 β m/e 305(47.76%)
 γ m/e 245(12.43%)
 m/e 77(1.29%)

Scheme 4

m.p. 164° (EtOH), ν_{\max} 3 120 (NH), 3 000–2 980 (aromatic and diphatic CH), 1 770, 1 680 (C=O), 1 630, 1 610 (C=C, C=N), 1 480, 1 450 (def. CH₂), 1 220 (CN), 870, 840 (aryl and phenyl groups) and 690 cm⁻¹ (C-I).

3,4-Disubstituted-5-dihydro-1,2,4-triazine-6-one (6) : A mixture of **2g** (0.005 mol) in dry pyridine (30 ml) and benzoyl chloride (0.01 mol) was stirred at 50° for 2 h, then cooled, poured onto crushed ice and acidified with HCl. The solid obtained was crystallised from ethanol, (30%), m.p. 266° (EtOH), ν_{\max} 3 500–3 150 (OH, NH), 3 090 (aromatic CH), 2 980 (aliphatic CH), 1 750, 1 680 (C=O), 1 620, 1 570 (C=C, C=N), 1 490, 1 460 (def. CH₂), 1 200 (CN), 980–920, 850, 810 cm⁻¹ (aryl and phenyl groups).

5-Dihydro-6-oxo-1,2,4-triazine[2,3-c]quinazoline (7) : A mixture of **2c** (0.01 mol) and ammonium acetate (0.05 mol) in glacial acetic acid (20 ml) was refluxed for 3 h, and then cooled. The solid obtained upon dilution with cold water was crystallised from glacial acetic acid, (40%), m.p. >300° (AcOH), ν_{\max} 3 400–3 200 (OH, NH), 3 100 (aromatic CH), 2 990 (aliphatic CH), 1 730 (C=O), 1 620, 1 600, 1 550 (C=C, C=N), 1 480–1 430 (def. CH₂), 1 200 (CN), 940–910, 840, 810 cm⁻¹ (aryl and phenyl groups).

1H-2,6-Tetrahydro-4-(6'-iodo-2'-phenyl-4'(3H)-quinazolinon-3'-yl)-1,4-diazin-3,5-dione (8) and **2,6-tetrahydro-4'-(6-iodo-2'-phenyl-4'(3H)-quinazolinon-3'-yl)-1,4-thiazin-3,5-dione (9)** : A mixture of **2c** (0.005 mol) and ethyl glycinate hydrochloride or mercaptoacetic acid (0.01 mol) in the presence of pyridine (30 ml) was refluxed for 8 h, then cooled, poured onto ice-HCl and filtered. The solid obtained was crystallised from ethanol : **8** (30%), m.p. 140° (EtOH) and **9** (40%), m.p. 312° (EtOH); ν_{\max} : 3 550–3 450 (OH), 3 050 (aromatic CH), 2 950, 2 890 (aliphatic CH), 1 710–1 150 (C=O), 1 620–1 610, 1 580–1 550 (C=C, C=N), 1 490, 1 470, 1 450 (def. CH₂), 1 250 (CN), 1 170 (C-S), 950, 870, 840 cm⁻¹ (aryl and phenyl groups).

2-Dihydro-4-(6'-iodo-2-phenyl-4'(3H)-quinazolinon-3'-yl)-1,4-thiazin-3,5-dione (10) : A suspension of **2e** (0.005 mol) in ethanol (30 ml) containing a few drops of pyridine was refluxed for 12 h, and then filtered while hot. The solvent was removed, cooled, poured onto ice-HCl and the resulting solid was washed with water and crystallised from ethanol, (30%), m.p. 263° (AcOH).

2-Imino-5-dihydro-1-(6'-iodo-2'-phenyl-4'(3H)-quinazolinon-3'-yl)-3-ethylcarboxypyrrol-5-one (11) : An

equimolar (0.005 mol) mixture of **2c** and ethyl cyanoacetate in piperidine (15 ml) was refluxed for 18 h, then cooled, diluted with water and acidified carefully. The separated solid was then crystallised from ethanol, (30%), m.p. 227° (EtOH); ν_{\max} 3 500–3 400 (OH), 3 150–3 100 (NH), 3 030–2 990 (aromatic CH), 2 980–2 950 (aliphatic CH), 1 750, 1 710, 1 690–1 670 (C=O), 1 640, 1 620 (C=C), 1 580–1 550 (C=N), 1 480–1 460, 1 440–1 420 (def. CH₂), 1 210 (CN), 1 090 (C–O–C), 980, 950, 840 cm⁻¹ (aryl and phenyl groups).

2-Imino-4-dihydro-1-(6-iodo-2'-phenyl-4'(3H)-quinazolinon-3'-yl)-3-cyano-5-one (12): A mixture of **2c** (0.005 mol) and malononitrile (0.01 mol) in piperidine (20 ml) was refluxed overnight, then cooled, and diluted with cold HCl. The resulting solid was crystallised, (35%), m.p. >300° (EtOH); ν_{\max} 3 500–3 400 (OH), 3 300–3 200 (NH), 3 050–2 980 (aromatic CH), 2 900 (aliphatic CH), 2 250–2 220 (C≡N), 1 700–1 650, 1 640–1 630 (C=O), 1 580, 1 550 (C=N), 1 490–1 450 (def. CH₂), 910, 870 cm⁻¹ (aryl and phenyl groups).

2-Dihydro-3-(6'-iodo-2'-phenyl-4'(3H)-quinazolinon-3'-yl)-1,4-oxazol-3,5-dione (13): A suspension of **2c** (0.005 mol) in ethanol (40 ml) and potassium cyanate (0.01 mol) was refluxed for 6 h, then filtered while hot, concentrated and cooled. The solid obtained was washed and crystallised from ethanol, (40%), m.p. 260° (EtOH).

The heterobicyclic systems 15a-e: An equimolar mixture of compound **1** and the required 3,1-4-benzoxazinone derivative (**14**) and anhydrous zinc chloride was fused at 180° for 30 min. The reaction mixture was then extracted with boiling glacial acetic acid, cooled and poured in ice-water. The solid obtained was dried and crystallised: **15a** (20%), m.p. 295° (AcOH); **15b** (30%), 252° (AcOH); **15c** (35%), 259° (AcOH); **15d** (20%), 243° (AcOH) and **15e** (25%), 210° (AcOH); ν_{\max} 3 010 (aromatic CH), 1 750–1 700 (C=O), 1 620, 1 600, 1 580 (C=C, C=N), 920, 850,

800 cm⁻¹ (aryl and phenyl groups); **15c** δ 7.16–7.29 and 7.35–7.45 (each 5H, m, phenyl), 8.04–8.09 and 8.70–8.71 (each 3H, m, ArH); **15b** m/z 632 (6.1%) molecular ion peak, 77 (100%) basic peak.

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